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Review Article

Pharmacognostic Evaluation Of Crude Drugs

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ABSTRACT

Ocimum Sanctum also known as Tulsi family of the ocimum sanctum is laminaceae. Ocimum sanctum are produced in India and Southeast Asia, India is the largest sources of medicinal plant in whole world. Herbs have been provided therapeutic potential to the health of individual. The demand of this plant are increasing day by day for medicinal purpose.¹ There are approximately 35,000 medicinal plants which are used for the therapeutic effect according to Ayurveda and siddha and unani and other traditional system. In which ocimum sanctum is one of the most important for medicinal purpose. It is employed in the treatment of various disease such as antimicrobial infection, antifungal, anticancer, arthritis, chronic fever, antifertility, eye disease, hepatoprotective, antispasmodic, and analgesic, antiemetic. Cardio protective.²

INTRODUCTION

This medicinal herb have also been shown to reduce blood glucose levels, making it an effective treatment of diabetes.^{3,4} There are many chemical constituent present in ocimum sanctum such as, oleanolic acid, rosmarinic acid, ursolic acid eugenol, linalool, carvacrol, □ elemene, □ caryophyllene, germacrene. Ocimum sanctum is considered to have diuretic, stimulant property.⁵ Volatile oil, fixed oil also obtained from the leaves of medicinal herbs.⁶ Monoterpene are obtained from the the volatile oils such as, camphene, myrcene, sabinene, in which some mono terpene produced oxygen such as linalool, borneol.⁷

Phytochemical analysis of this medicinal herb can identify the nature of compounds present in the extract of ocimum sanctum. It is also for identify the bioactive compound and their effect. They are commonly helpful as model for the synthetic of new Medicine.⁸ Tulsi is an important symbol of the Hindu religious tradition. Although the word „Tulsi“ gives the connotation of the incomparable one, its other name, Vishnupriya means the one that pleases Lord Vishnu. Found in most of the Indian homes and worshipped, its legend has permeated Indian ethos down the ages. Known in English as Holy Basil and botanically called Ocimum sanctum, Tulsi belongs to plant family

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Lamiaceae.⁹ It has made important contribution to the field of science from ancient times as also to modern research due to its large number of medicinal properties. Tulsi has been described as of two types- vanya (wild) and gramya (grown in homes). Although having identical usage, the former has darker leaves. Tulsi is a popular home remedy for many ailments such as wound, bronchitis, liver diseases, catarrhal fever, otalgia, lumbago, hiccough, ophthalmia, gastric disorders, genitourinary disorders, skin diseases, various forms of poisoning and psychosomatic stress disorders.^{10,11} It has also aromatic, stomachic, carminative, demulcent, diaphoretic, diuretic, expectorant, alexiteric, vermifuge and febrifuge properties. In view of these facts, an attempt has been made to review on the various pharmacological activities of OS based on the experimental and clinical studies reported in different literatures. Tulsi grows wild in the tropics and warm regions. The plant is distributed and cultivated throughout India. It is an erect, much branched, fragrant and erected plant attaining a height of about 30-60 cm when mature. Its aromatic leaves are simple, opposite, elliptic, oblong, obtuse or acute with entire or subserrate or dentate margins, growing up to 5 cm long. The Tulsi flowers are small, purplish in elongate racemes in close whorls. The fruits are small and the seeds are reddish- yellow in colour. The plant is bitter and acrid⁹⁻¹⁰. Traditional uses: Tulsi is also known as "the elixir of life" since it promotes long.^{12,13} India is well known as an "Emporium of medicinal plants". It possesses about 8% of the estimated biodiversity of the world with around 12600 species and is one of the 12 mega biodiversity centers with 2 hot spots of biodiversity in the Western Ghats and North-eastern region.¹⁴ It's also rich in ethnic diversity, there are about 67.37 million tribal people belonging to 537 tribal groups living in different geographical locations with various subsistence

patterns.¹⁵ These tribal groups living in diverse, rich areas possess a wealth of knowledge and skills on the utilization and conservation of food and medicinal plants.¹⁶ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), almost 65% of the world's population has incorporated the value of plants as a methodology of medicinal agents into their primary modality of health care. It is often noted that 25% of all drugs prescribed today come from plants.¹⁷ This estimate suggests that plant derived drugs make up a significant segment of natural product- based pharmaceuticals. Plants have long been used by men for their basic needs especially *Ocimum sanctum*. In essence have been in practices of medicinal plants are deeply rooted in the society of indigenous community.^{18,19} Medicinal plants begins an important aspect of various traditional medicine systems, have been used therapeutically all around the world. Although the various systems of traditional medicine in the world, e.g., Ayurveda, Chinese traditional medicine, Unani, Tibetan Medicine, Amazonian or African Medicine, may be based on different theoretical and cultural models, they all integrate phytotherapy into their doctrine.²⁰ According to World Health Organization (WHO) estimates, more than 80% of the people in developing countries depend on the traditional medicine for their countries depend on the traditional medicine for their primary health needs.²¹ It is generally estimated that over 6000 traditional plants in India are used in folk and herbal medicine, representing about 75% of the medicinal needs of the 3rd world countries. Aromatic plants possess odorous volatile substances which occur as essential oil, gumexudate, balsam and oleoresin in one or more parts, namely root, wood, bark, stem, foliage, flower and fruit. The characteristic aroma is due to a variety of complex chemical compound. The essential oil is concomitant to fragrance or perfumes because these fragrance are oily in

nature and they represent the essence or the active constituents of the plant.²² They are called volatile or ethereal oils as they evaporate when exposed to air at ordinary temperatures. Essential oils are highly concentrated, low volume, high value products. Application of essential oils in agriculture as antifeedants, repellents, botanical insecticides, natural herbicides and growth booster are still open to fascinating realms of research.²³ Essential oils of only about 500 species are known in some detail at present. Of these about 50 species find use as commercial source of essential oils and aroma chemicals, through the number of those having regular and large scale utilization hardly exceeds two dozens.²⁴ Phytochemicals (from the Greek word phyto, meaning plant) are biologically active, naturally occurring chemical compounds found in plants, which provide health benefits for humans further than those attributed to macronutrients and micronutrients.²⁵ They protect plants from disease and damage and contribute to the plant's color, aroma and flavor. In general, the plant chemicals that protect plant cells from environmental hazards such as pollution, stress, drought, UV exposure and pathogenic attack are called as phytochemicals.²⁶ Recently, it is clearly known that they have roles in the protection of human health, when their dietary intake is significant. More than 4,000 phytochemicals have been catalogued and are classified by protective function, physical characteristics and chemical characteristics and About 150 phytochemicals have been studied in detail. In wide-ranging dietary phytochemicals are found in fruits, vegetables, legumes, whole grains, nuts, seeds, fungi, herbs and spices. Broccoli, cabbage, carrots, onions, garlic, whole wheat bread, tomatoes, grapes, cherries, strawberries, raspberries, beans, legumes, and soy foods are common sources.²⁷ Phytochemicals accumulate in different parts of the plants, such as in the roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits or seeds. Many

phytochemicals, particularly the pigment molecules, are often concentrated in the outer layers of the various plant tissues. Levels vary from plant to plant depending upon the variety, processing, cooking and growing condition. Phytochemicals are also available in supplementary forms, but evidence is lacking that they provide the same health benefits as dietary phytochemical.

Fig1.1 Tulsi Plant

History:

Tulsi, botanical, and in vitro tissue culture techniques in *Ocimum sanctum* Linn., a medicinal herb used in the indigenous system of medicine. Tulsi has been adored in almost all ayurvedic literature for its adorable medicinal properties. It is pungent-bitter in taste. Its leaves are hot, light and dry while seeds are considered to be cold in effect. Several medicinal properties of Tulsi are present in the roots, leaves and seeds. It has a wide range of action on the human body mainly aim curing cough, inducer of sweat and prevents the indigestion and anorexia. Medicinal properties of Tulsi are very well known for thousand years to various parts of the world. In the Indian subcontinent, Hindus considered this medicinal herb as sacred plant. Exploration the scientific studies of traditional belief of medicinal properties of Tulsi have got acceleration after the middle of the 20th century. Most of the evidences are based upon in-vitro, experimental and a very few are of human studies. It is an aromatic plant. Plants have served human kind as sources of medicinal agents since its earliest beginnings. In fact natural product

once served as the source of all drugs. The main chemical constituents of Tulsi are: Oleanolic acid, Ursolic acid, Rosmarinic acid, Eugenol, Carvacrol, Linalool, and β -caryophyllene, have been used extensively for many years in food products, perfumery, and dental and oral products and plant extract continues the numerous searches for more effective drugs of plant origin which are less toxic and available for low socio-economic population in the treatment of diseases caused by pathogenic bacteria. that Tulsi may be a COX-2 inhibitor, like many modern painkillers, due to its high concentration of eugenol. evaluate the phytochemical screening of aqueous extracts of leaves of *Ocimum*. It has been shown that this medicinal herbs can be used as pharmaceutical adjuvants in the formulation of various dosage form.

1. Morphological Attributes:

Tulsi is an annual herb 35-70 cm high, branched stems usually purple in colour, sub- quadrangular, clothed with soft spreading hairs. Leaves are 2.5-5 cm. long and 1.7-3.3 cm broad, acute obtuse or oblong, elliptical, margin serrate or entire, surface pubescent on both sides, gland dotted, base acute or obtuse, 1.3-2.5 cm petioles, long slender, hairy. Flowers in present in racemes 15-20 cm forming verticillaster inflorescence. long and broad bracts with 3mm diameter, broadly ovate; slender calyx, pubescent, bilabiate, lower lip is longer than upper lip. Corolla 4 mm long, purple in colour, bilabiate upper lip pubescent on the back. Stamens are exserted, slender filaments , the upper pair with a small appendage having a branch present at the base.²⁸ Nutlets are 1.26 mm long, broadly ellipsoid, smooth, p yellow with black markings. Seeds are brownish, globose or subglobose. Aromatic od our and Sharpe Taste ²⁹

Fig 2.1 Parts of Tulsi Plant

1. Deepika Gulati¹ *, Priyanka, Minakshi Pal, Nidhi, Ikbal etl was studied Pharmacognostic evaluation of crude drug. This review will definitely help the researchers who deals with Tulsi studies to know its use in proper way, herb appears to be highly valuable due to many pharmacological / medicinal properties.
2. Govind Pandey^{1*} and Madhuri S.² etl was studied Pharmacognostic evaluation of crude drug . The roots, leaves and seeds of Tulsi possess several medicinal properties. Ayurvedic texts categorise OS as stimulant, aromatic and antipyretic. While alleviating kapha and vata, it aggravates pitta. It has a wide range of action on the human body mainly as a cough alleviator, a sweat-inducer and a mitigator of indigestion and anorexia.
3. Priya Panchal* and Nayyar Parvez etl was studied Pharmacognostic evaluation of crude drug It is an aromatic plant. Plants have served human kind as sources of medicinal agents since its earliest beginnings. In fact natural product once served as the source of all drugs.
4. Shankar Mondal¹, Bijay R. Mirdha² And Sushil C. Mahapatra^{1*} etl was studied Pharmacognostic evaluation of crude drug : Medicinal properties of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum* Linn) are known for thousand years to various civilizations of the world. This medicinal herb is considered as a sacred plant by the Hindus in the Indian subcontinent.
5. Harichandan SS Priyadarshini , Sahu Ajay Kumar , *, Gautam Sakshi and Nemani Rahul etl was studied Pharmacognostic evaluation of crude

drug The phytochemicals present in plants are responsible for preventing disease and promoting health have been studied extensively to establish their efficacy and to understand the underlying mechanism of their action.

Material And Method: -

- **Collection of plant Material:** Leaves of Ocimum Sanctum L.(Tulsi) Were Collected From Different Sites of Bhigwan
- **Chemicals:** Mayer reagent, Wagner’s reagent, Lead ethanoate, Alkaline reagent, Ferric chloride, Molisch’s reagent, Alkaline reagent, Barford’s reagent, Iodine solution, Ninhydrin solution, sodium hydroxide, all chemicals were used to find out the presence of phytochemical constituents which were obtained.³⁰
- **Plant Material:** Fresh Leaves of selected medicinal herb Ocimum sanctum (Tulsi) was harvested from the herbal garden. The collected leaves were thoroughly washed with tap water to avoid dusts and other unwanted materials accumulated on the leaves from their natural environment. The dust free leaves were shade, dried at room temperature. After 4-5 days for obtaining aqueous extract, the properly dried leaves were then grinding into the fine powder by using the grinding machine than the powder material of tulsi leaves were weighed properly. The fine powder of tulsi leaves was stored in a clean and tightly closed container for extraction.³¹

Table. 3.2 Plant Material of Kingdom Plantae

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Lamiales
Division	Magnoliophyta
Super division	Spermatophyte Seed Plants
Genus	Ocimum L.
Species	O. tenuiflorum
Family	Lamiaceae

- **Preparation of aqueous extract of Ocimum sanctum (leaves):**

The extract of leaves were obtained in sufficient quantity by using distilled water. In this process firstly 20 g powdered leaves of ocimum sanctum were placed in 200 ml of beaker and 100 ml of distilled was poured into beaker after addition of water kept for overnight at the room temperature approximately 22 hrs for thorough mixing and also complete elucidation of active materials to dissolve in the respective solvent then, extract was filtered by using muslin cloth followed by Whatman no 1 filter paper then the green colour filtrate was obtained, after done this process filtrate was dried. Finally, the residues were collected and used for the experiment³². Aqueous extract of ocimum sanctum leaves which is used in the various treatment. Fresh juice of Tulsi leaves is employ in karma. This technique helps to ease headache and diseases of head and neck. Tulsi leaves act as nerving tonic. Tulsi leaves extract reduces pimples, acne and scars effectively.

Fig4.1. Aqueous Extract of Tulsi

Organoleptic characterization of aqueous extract:

The colour, odour, texture, taste, fracture of ocimum sanctum (Tulsi) were characterized . Phytochemical analysis of aqueous extract of ocimum sanctum- The aqueous extract of ocimum sanctum was subjected to phytochemical analysis find out the presence and absence of phytochemical constituents. Flavonoid synthesis in plants is induced by light colour spectrums at both high and low energy radiations. Low energy radiations are accepted by phytochrome, while high energy radiations are accepted by

carotenoids, flavins, cryptochromes in addition to phytochromes.³³ The phytochemical tests employed for alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, proteins, fixed oil, carbohydrate and tannins, Cardiac glycosides, saponins and flavonoids and terpenoids.

Fig 5.1. Tulsi Powder

Evaluation Parameters:

1. Test for alkaloids:

1. Mayer's test:

- 5 mg extract of *Ocimum Sanctum* (Tulsi) was transferred in the test tube and then added 1% hydrochloric acid HCl, the obtained solution was gently heated. Red colour indicate the presence of alkaloids because Potassium mercuric iodine are present in Mayer's reagent. Wagner's test- In this test 5 mg extract of *ocimum sanctum* was taken in a test tube than 0.5 of wagner reagent was added in a solution shaken well. Apperance of reddish brown colour showing the alkaloids are present. Reddish brown colour beacause of iodine forms a complax is insoluble and has the colour brown redish.

2. Dragendorff test:

-5 mg extract of *ocimum sanctum tulsi* was taken in tube. And then one drop of dragendroff reagent was added in the test tube. orange-red colour, showing the presence of alkaloids. Dragendroff reagent was prepared using Bismuth nitrate, Nitric acid, iodine and water because of these chemicals it gives orange red colour in the preseance of alkaloids. ³⁴

2. Test for flavonoids:

Shinoda test:

Firstly 5mg extract was added in the test tube then small amount of magnesium was mixed in this solution, also added the the few drops of concentrated Hydrochloric acid. It should be indicate the pink colour with the flavonoids. Colours varying from orange to red indicated flavones, red to crimson indicated flavonoids, crimson to magenta indicated flavonones. Catechins when treated with vanillin solution in hydrochloric acid give red pink colour.

Lead ethanoate test for flavonoids-

placed 5 mg of aqueous extract of tulsi in test tube then 1ml of lead ethanoate solution was added. It gives the buff coloured solution if the alkaloids are present.

Sodium hydroxide test for flavonoids-

5 mg extract was taken in this 1 ml of the 10% solution of sodium hydroxide was added for appearance of yellow colour solution after addition of 1ml of dilute Hydrochloric acid, in the presence of alkaloids the colour should be changed from yellow to colourless after addition of 2 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid.

Alkaline reagent test for flavonoids-

5 mg extract of *ocimum sanctum* was placed in the test tube mixed than the 2ml of 2% solution of Sodium hydroxide was poured in it, if the formation of yellow which turned into colourless after addition of few drops of diluted acetic. It means that alkaloids are present in the holy basil Ferric chloride test- Ferric chloride test was performed for checking the presence of flavonoids in the aqueous extract of *ocimum sanctum*. Firstly 5 mg extract was mixed with 1ml of distilled water than 0.5ml of dilute ammonia solution was added into it. After addition of dilute ammonia few drops of concentrated Sulfuric acid was mixed later. Formation of yellowish with flavonoids.³⁵

3. Test for glycoside:

Liebermann's test:

Liebermann's test for the analysis of glycoside are present or not in aqueous extract of *ocimum*

sanctum in this test 5 mg extract of ocimum sanctum was mixed properly with 2ml of chloroform and then 2ml of acetic acid were mixed in the. Solution than it was cooled in ice. After cooling 1 ml of concentrated Sulfuric acid was added. The colour will be change from violet to green with the presence of alkaloids in the extract.

Salkowski's test:

for the analysis of glycoside 2ml of chloroform were with 1ml of extract. Then 2ml of concentrated Sulfuric acid were added and shaken gently. A reddish brown colour indicated the presence of glycoside

Keller-kilani test for cardiac glycosides:

for the confirmation of the glycoside in the extract 5 mg extract was taken in the test tubes than the 1 ml of glacial acetic acid was added. Few drop of 2% solution of ferric chloride were mixed into it. Then 1 ml of concentrated Sulfuric acid were into the mixture. A brown colour ring at the edge will be formed in the presence cardiac glycosides.³⁶

4. Test for tannins:

Ferric chloride test-

5 mg aqueous extract of ocimum sanctum was mixed with 0.5 ml of ferric chloride solution. Formation of blackish precipitate in the presence of tannin

Gelatine test-

gelatine test was performed for checking the presence of tannin in the extract. In this test 5 mg extract was mixed with gelatine and 1ml of water was added into the solution. White precipitate should be produced.

Lead acetate

- lead acetate test was performed to estimate the presence of tannin in which 5 mg of test samples was taken in test tubes. Few drops of basic lead acetate was added in the sample solution, if brown bulky precipitate will be found it means tannin are present in test sample.³⁷

5. Test for saponins:

Foam test was performed for identification of saponin in the aqueous extract in which 1ml extract was dissolved into the 5ml of distilled water. After addition of distilled water it was shaken for proper mixing till foam was observed. Few foam was added with 2 drops of olive oil and it was shaken vigorously. It should be produced emulsion with the saponins.³⁹

6. Test for oil:

Stain test:

few quantity of aqueous extract was spread onto the filter paper formation of oil on the filter paper will indicate the presence of oil in aqueous.

7. Saponification test:

Few drops of alcoholic potassium hydroxide and 0.5 ml of extract were taken into test tube and mixed well. 1-4 drops of phenolphthalein were added into the mix solution. It was heated on water bath hours for 1 hour. Formation of partial neutralization of alkali which indicates the presence of oils and fats.⁴⁰

8. Test for carbohydrates:

Benedict's test:

Benedict's reagent was taken for the analysis of carbohydrate. the 5 mg extract was mixed with few drops of benedict's reagent, than allowed to boiled, the reddish brown precipitate are found with the presence of the carbohydrates (absent).

Molisch's test:

initially 5 mg extract was taken in test tube than the 1 ml of Molisch's reagent was added into it. Mixture was shaken properly. After that, 2ml of concentrated Sulfuric acid was poured carefully along the side of the test tube. Appearance of a violet ring at the interface indicated the presence of carbohydrate.⁴¹

9. Test for steroids:

5 mg extract of ocimum sanctum was mixed with 1 ml of chloroform then few drops of concentrated Sulfuric acid and acetic acid were added into it. The greenish colour was indicate the presence of steroids.

Salkowski's test:

3 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was added into the 5 mg extract. The formation of red colour indicates the presence of steroids.

10. Test for proteins:**Biuret's test:**

5 mg extract was added with the few drops of biuret's reagent. The obtained mixture was shaken well and allowed to warm for 1-5 min. Appearance of red or violet colour indicated presence of proteins

Million's test:

5 mg extract was mixed with 2ml of Mallon's reagent. The solution was heated for 5 min red colour precipitated turns into red colour which confirmed the presence of protein.

Ninhydrin test:

aqueous extract of tulsi was mixed with 2 ml of 0.2% solution of Ninhydrin and boiled for 2 min on water bath, if violet colour appeared with the presence of amino acids and proteins in the aqueous extract.⁴¹

RESULT:

Phytochemical studies Qualitative phytochemical investigation discovered presence of alkaloids compounds Appearance of red colour, flavonoids and tannins The pink colour shows the presence of flavonoids and blackish precipitate indicated the

presence of tannins and absence of flavonoids Not observed pink coloration in all mentioned extracts of plant. Salkowski's test- formation of brownishred colour showed positive result for aqueous extract. It showed negative result in case of protein, saponin, oil, steroids. Flavonoid has also been reported to have greater potential benefit to human Health. The medicinal plants ocimum sanctum is being used traditionally for the treatment of inflammation, wound healing, toothache, antiseptics, carminative, cough, expectorant, stomatitis and some fungal infection. The antibacterial activity has been attributed to the presence of some active constituents in the extracts. The phytochemical screening of aqueous leaf extract of O. sanctum, revealed the presence and absence of alkaloids, flavonoids and tannin compounds showed that organoleptic characteristics of ocimum sanctum.

Fig.6.1. Evaluation Parameter of Ocimum Sanctum Extract

Table:6.2 Qualitative Evaluation of Phytochemical In The Ocimum Sanctum Extract

Phytochemicals	Test	Inference
Alkaloids	Mayer's	Present
	Wagner's	Present
Flavonoids	Sodium Hydroxide Test	Present
	Shinoda test	Present
	Alkaline Reagent Test	Present
	Ferric Chloride Test	Present
Glycosides	Liebermann's test	Absent
	Salkowski's Test	Absent
	Keller-Killani Test	Absent
Tannin	Ferric Chloride Test	Present
	Gelatin Test	Present
Saponin	Foam Test	Present
Oil	Stain Test	Absent
Carbohydrate	Saponification Test	Absent
	Molisch's Test	Absent

	Benedict's Test	Absent
Steroids	Chloroform Test	Absent
	Salkowski's Test	Absent
Test for Proteins	Biuret's Test	Absent
	Million's Test	Absent
	Ninhydrin Test	Absent

CONCLUSION:

The obtained result from whole study confirm the validity of the use of *Ocimum sanctum* plant as medicine in ancient medicinal traditions and suggest that some of the plant extracts possess compounds with antimicrobial properties. *circilineol*, *circimaritin*, *isothymusin*, *apigenin* and *rosameric acid*, are present in isolated aqueous extract of *ocimum sanctum* which may be useful against fever, syphilitic, ulcer, inflammatory disease wounds, such as antimicrobial infection, analgesic, antifungal, arthritis, anticancer, eye disease, antifertility, hepatoprotective, chronic fever, antispasmodic, antiemetic, cardio protective etc. In protective antioxidant supplement *ocimum sanctum* leaf extract may be used after the analysis of certain tests. After this study it is assumed that the extract could be used for the new formulations and potent antimicrobial drugs of natural origin.

Table.7.1. Organoleptic characterization of *ocimum sanctum*.

Sr. No	Organoleptic Properties	Observation
1	Colour	Green
2	Odour	Aromatic
3	Taste	Slightly Pungent
4	Texture	Smooth

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